

BRIEF CONSIDERATIONS REGARDING THE SPECIFICS OF THE CURRICULUM IN THE CURRENT ROMANIAN EDUCATION LAW

Adrian NICOLESCU¹

¹University of Craiova, Craiova, Romania

Abstract

Recently, the educational system in Romania has faced a series of changes, not only legislative, but also social changes, all of which are intended to make the educational act more flexible and adapt it to the new requirements imposed at the global level. The definition of the concept of curriculum has aroused interest both in the specialized literature from Romania and abroad, offering numerous definitions, some of which are more than comprehensive. The clarification of the curriculum concept was not neglected by the old national education law no. 1/2011, nor by the current law on pre-university education no. 198/2023. The last normative act, in force at the time of writing this article, the pre-university education law no. 198/2023, provides educational actors with a much broader definition compared to the old regulation.

Keywords: curriculum, legislation, educational actors, resilience

Currently, society is one characterised by globalization dominated by changes on all levels, especially in the educational field. This field has undergone numerous changes lately, and the most impactful are those of a legislative nature, aimed at creating order and predictability at the level of the educational act. The changes that have occurred have established in the task of educational experts and not only the imperative obligation to do all the diligence to create a framework with increased resilience to all obstacles, events and unforeseen challenges that arise. Educational experts have the essential role of creating a curriculum adapted to the current needs of society.

The importance of the curriculum at the level of the educational system is known to everyone, and this has determined that many specialists strive to crystallize the notion. In Ungureanu's opinion, "the curriculum is much more flexible, adaptable and reconfigurable to the needs of society and learners, overcoming the teaching-learning duality (Ungureanu, 1999, pp. 21-25 apud Strungă, 2020, p 11)

A general definition of the notion of curriculum implies "a set of components with an educational purpose, the articulation of which allows the orientation and operationalization of a system through pedagogical and administrative action plans. It is anchored in historical, social, linguistic, political, religious, geographical and cultural realities of a country, region or locality. (Jonnaert & Ettayebi & Defise, 2010, p 70 apud Nicu, 2013, p 106)

Instead, the pre-university education law no. 198/2023 in article 85, paragraph 7 makes available to all educational actors a clear and concise definition of the national curriculum as "the current set of elements that regulate the activity of teaching staff in pre-university education and includes education framework plans, school programs and national assessment standards."

In accordance with the provisions of art 88, paragraph 1 of the Pre-University Education Law no. 198/2023 school programs are closely related to the educational framework plans. Thus, school programs, in accordance with the provisions of the education framework plans, establish the educational offer for study subjects considering a time budget and a determined school path. At the same time, the Ministry of Education, through the competent bodies and institutions, elaborates the educational framework plans and school programs for the study subjects and mandatory training modules in pre-university education. (art. 88, para. 2 of Law no. 198/2023)

As a new element, the current law on pre-university education includes in the national curriculum architecture, the national evaluation standards, which are important tools available to teachers. The evaluation process being quite complex and requiring sustained effort on the part of the teaching staff, "is carried out on the basis of the national evaluation standards for each discipline, field of study and mode of training." (art. 95, paragraph 2 of Law no. 198/2023)

In the current legislation on pre-university education, the goals of the assessment are clearly and concisely provided, thus in accordance with the provisions of art. 95 paragraph 1 of the Pre-University Education Law no. 198/2023, "the goals of the evaluation are the orientation and optimization of the teaching-learning process, as well as the management of one's own learning results."

If are situations encountered in schools where teachers do not evaluate students in accordance with national evaluation standards or in accordance with evaluation methodologies, and in these cases, the legislator has provided that these facts constitute disciplinary misconduct and are sanctioned in accordance with the rigors of the law. (art. 96, paragraph 3 of Law no. 198/2023)

In accordance with the provisions of article 85 paragraph 8 of the Pre-University Education Law no. 198/2023, the implementation of the national curriculum is carried out through support tools, namely alternative school textbooks and specific application methodologies. In the opinion of Professor Negreț-Dobridor:,, the school manual is the most important work tool for students, closely following the analytical curriculum, describing in an appropriate language everything that is necessary for students to be able to achieve the pedagogical objectives established by the school curriculum under the defined conditions through general and specific pedagogical principles." (Negreț-Dobridor, 2008, p. 230 apud Strungă, 2020, p. 202)

According to the specialists, the textbook as a support tool for the curriculum must have a minimum required content and it must contain the pedagogical objectives pursued, explicit or implicit, however present; tasks, exercises, problems; information for carrying out the learning tasks as much as possible clear and suggestive (accompanied by illustrations, schemes); additional tasks to deepen the study; additional sources to supplement knowledge (audio-video); self-assessment exercises, lists. (Potolea & Manolescu, 2006)

It can be easily seen that, in the current legislation, the role of the national curriculum is to facilitate the learning process by offering at the level of pre-university education, "learning opportunities for students, so that everyone can capitalize on their potential, depending on their training, needs and interests of knowledge, with a view to integration and active participation in society." (art. 85 paragraph 6 of Law no. 198/2023)

Similar to what happened in the past, in the current context, educational policies in Romania are influenced by an accumulation of political, legislative, economic and cultural factors. (Nicu, 2013, p. 60)

The main objective of the educational policies regarding the curriculum counts in "structuring it in such a way as to really ensure the premises for the differentiation and individualization of learning experiences, for the formation of the skills necessary for fulfillment and development throughout life." (Nicu, 2013, p. 108)

In addition to the main objective of educational policies regarding the national curriculum, we emphasize that it is important to highlight the importance of curriculum objectives. In the specialized literature, curricular objectives are "elements of clear and precise intentionality, which aim at changes in the student's behavior, performance and benefit, in the form of new acquisitions, from one educational situation to another, provided that these changes and acquisitions be observable and, as far as possible, measurable by the educator." (Ungureanu, 1999, p 133 apud Strungă, 2020, p 102)

Curricular objectives can be quantified and examined by all educational actors, not only by educational experts regarding concrete and very practical aspects. (Strungă, 2020, p. 102)

The consolidation and structuring of a national curriculum that meets the rigorous educational requirements has always aroused increased interest regardless of the context, and the construction is not an easy process, on the contrary, it represents "an extremely complex activity involving a series of factors, the priority factors being policies, because the political context determines the goals of the educational system, respectively the functional dimension of the education process; social factors, because they determine the needs of the education system according to social conditions, the diversity of educational environments, the index of disparity between urban and rural areas, the integration of children from economically disadvantaged areas; demographic factors characterize the school population by reference to different indices - gross

and net level of schooling, the percentage of literacy, school dropout (...), a definition of the external effectiveness and the internal effectiveness of an educational system." (Jonnaert & Ettayebi & Defise, 2010, p 48 apud Nicu, 2013, p 106)

Pre-university education law no. 198/2023 modifies the organization of the education system in Romania as "the National Center for Curriculum and Evaluation (CNCE) and the Institute of Education Sciences are established as separate entities. These institutions will be responsible for developing the curriculum, coordinating the national assessment and examination system to monitor the school results of students, as well as carrying out independent research to inform the development and evaluation of public policies." (Fordham&Abadia, 2023, p. 8)

At the request of the Romanian Ministry of Education, the Organization for Cooperation and Economic Development has drawn up a report by which it provides guidelines to continue the reform in education started within the project "Educated Romania". Through the "Educated Romania" project, we aim to "make Romania a resilient and high-performing country, where access to quality education is ensured for every student and where teachers are mentors and professionals who continuously improve themselves in order to respond to the emerging needs of the national and global curriculum." (Fordham&Abadia, 2023, p. 4)

In the framework of the "Educated Romania" project initiated by the President of Romania, one of the priority areas concern curriculum and evaluation centered on competences. This priority area for our country requires competence-centered curriculum design; increasing curricular flexibility; curriculum monitoring and evaluation; the foundation of transversal skills related to education for health, for sustainability, for democracy/society, including in the

field of financial and legal education. The assessment of pupils/students will be centered on competences, the development of standards and descriptors, the increase of the role of assessment in the training of teaching staff, the digitization of assessment, the provision of feedback, etc. (<http://www.romaniaeducata.eu/despre/>)

At the European level, a series of key skills are promoted, which require the national curriculum for primary, secondary and high school education to focus on them in order to determine the student's training profile: reading, writing and message comprehension skills; multilingual skills; mathematical competence and competence in science, technology and engineering; digital competence, including internet safety and cyber security; personal, social and learning competence; civic, legal and environmental competence; entrepreneurial competence; awareness-raising and cultural expression. (art. 91 of Law no. 198/2023)

Conclusions

The recent legislative changes in the field of education came in the context in which Romania, as a member state of the European Union, assumed the obligation to harmonize domestic legislation with international legislation.

If in the past, there was only one national education, namely law no. 1/2011, currently the Romanian legislature has adopted two education laws, one for pre-university education no. 198/2023, and one containing provisions regarding university education, namely law no. 199/2023. All these recent legislative changes have the role of creating a predictable and balanced education system for both teachers and students.

In order to keep up with changes at the level of society, but also with the dynamism of the labor market, the current curriculum in Romania has been

largely reformed in recent years. Curricular reform was a necessary process because it represents "the core of the educational system, but also its manifestation framework." (Nicu, 2013, p. 101)

The effort made by educational experts to reform the curriculum over time has not always been crowned with success. Alexandru Crișan, in his work, makes an analysis of the curriculum changes pointing out that it „characterizes these transition years by a zig-zag walk, with ups and downs, reform and counter-reform measures that followed each other over time, not allowing clear outlining, lasting and sustainable educational policies and strategies." (Crișan, 2006)

Therefore, all the new aspects introduced by the new regulations in the educational field are important to create a framework conducive to the development of all students regardless of the environment in which they have to study, be it rural or urban, and to eliminate the disparities created between them.

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